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European Green Deal: Creating a New Agricultural Production Model

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Abstract: European Green Deal is the European Union's strategic plan to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. It aims to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy, ensuring no net greenhouse gas emissions, economic growth decoupled from resource use, and inclusivity so that no person or place is left behind. Key initiatives include investing in environmentally friendly technologies, supporting industry innovation, and promoting cleaner, cheaper, and healthier forms of private and public transport. By implementing these measures, the EU seeks to lead the global fight against climate change and protect the natural environment for future generations. (<https://commission.europa.eu/>, 2025a). The present research paper is an initial study to identify the main objectives of the European Green Deal strategy and their aspects on the creation of a sustainable economy.

Keywords: European Green Deal, agricultural production model, sustainable development, european policy

Introduction

Climate change and environmental degradation are challenges that our world is facing today. In this context, the European Green Deal is an ambitious and innovative effort by the European Union to promote sustainable development and address the environmental challenges that threaten the future of the planet. To overcome these challenges, the European Green Deal will try to transform the European Union, into a modern, resource - efficient and competitive economy, by ensuring no net emission of greenhouse gases by 2050, economic growth decoupled from resource use and no person and no place left behind. (<https://commission.europa.eu/>, 2025a) The Green Deal aims to achieve a low-carbon economy, reduce energy consumption and protect natural resources, while pursuing economic growth and social well-being. In this text, we will study the main principles and objectives of the European Green Deal on agriculture and the creation of a sustainable economy.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The purpose of this text is to study and present the principles and objective of the European Green Deal (EGD) regarding agriculture and the creation of a sustainable economy. It is well known that the EU with the implementation of the EGD, is trying to achieve a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system in the European Union (Guyomard., H., et. al., 2023). The EGD, concerns all sectors of the European economy, including energy, transport, agriculture and industry. Also, agriculture, is at the center of the European Union's strategic actions, and the launch of EGD marks the new big vision of the EU, for the creation of a healthy food system for people and the planet (Goulas., A., and Papachatzis., A., 2024a). According to Kotyza (2023), the direction of many European Policies, after the year 2019, has been focused on the climate change and how to deal with it. Furthermore, the EU's main agriculture policy objectives are to:

- ensure farmers get a better revenue from the market to produce sufficient quantities of safe food, respecting EU rules on sustainability, animal welfare, traceability, etc.
- provide farm businesses with support systems to help stabilize their incomes in the face of less predictable production conditions
- make farming attractive to encourage young people to join
- facilitate investment in an innovative, competitive, sustainable farming sector
- maintain viable rural communities, with diverse economies
- create and maintaining jobs throughout the food chain (https://commission.europa.eu, 2025b).

According to Pawlowski and Soltysiak, (2024), the European Green Deal is the EU's response to the Sustainable Development Goals and is primarily intended to counteract the climate crisis and furthermore keep the balance of food security worldwide. Many academics claim that the EGD commits the EU to a change in policy direction towards a more sustainable economy and sustainability (Bongardt and Torres, 2022). EGD and other key pillars such as Farm - to - Fork strategy, are offering a sustainable solution for food systems and offer various benefits for rural communities (Goulas and Papachatzis, 2024b).

Research Results

The analysis of the European Green Deal (EGD) highlights its critical role in transforming the EU into a sustainable and climate-neutral economy. The research findings indicate that agriculture and food systems play a central role in achieving the EGD's objectives, emphasizing sustainable farming practices, food security, and rural community development. The study confirms that the EGD aims to ensure fair income for farmers, promote eco-friendly agricultural methods, and enhance food system resilience.

Furthermore, the research supports the argument that the EGD's integration with policies such as the Farm-to-Fork strategy provides a comprehensive approach to sustainability. Investments in environmentally friendly technologies, sustainable food production, and circular economy principles are seen as essential components in achieving the EU's climate goals. However, several challenges remain significant barriers to implementation of the EU's ambitious strategy. Farmers and agribusinesses claim to need more financial support and financial investments. That is the reason for the new strategic dialogue on the future of EU agriculture, that has been launched in January 2024 (<https://commission.europa.eu>, 2025c). In response to farmers' concerns, the Commission has presented options to reduce the administrative burden on EU farmers, and is working on actions to improve the position of farmers in the food chain and to improve the enforcement against unfair trading practices. It has also launched two surveys: a first one where farmers and all smaller suppliers across the food supply chain can share their views on their experience with unfair trading practices, and a second one to gather farmers' views on simplifying certain rules and procedures (<https://commission.europa.eu>, 2025c).

Moreover, the results highlight that the EGD's objectives can work together with the broader Sustainable Development Goals, aiming to mitigate climate change while ensuring economic growth and social well-being. If the EGD strategy will be implemented with success by the EU's countries members, can become a global model for sustainability, demonstrating how economic development and environmental protection can coexist effectively.

Conclusions

The European Green Deal is an ambitious and necessary step towards a sustainable economy and tackling climate change. Its targets to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, protect biodiversity and promote a circular economy are crucial prerequisites for achieving sustainable development. However, its implementation comes with significant challenges, requiring coordinated action at European and national level, as well as significant investments in new technologies and infrastructure. The European Green Deal is not only a solution for sustainable development, but also a model for the rest of the world. If Europe manages to achieve its ambitious goals, it can act as a model for other countries and regions to follow its lead towards a more sustainable and climate-neutral economy.

References

- Bongardt, A., & Torres, F. (2022). The European Green Deal: More than an exit strategy to the pandemic crisis, a building block of a sustainable European economic model. *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 60, 170-185.
- European Commission. (2025a). The European Green Deal. Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en.
- European Commission. (2025b). Agriculture and rural development. Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/topics/agriculture-and-rural-development_en.
- European Commission. (2025c). Strategic dialogue on the future of EU agriculture. Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/topics/agriculture-and-rural-development/strategic-dialogue-future-eu-agriculture_en.
- Goulas, A., & Papachatzis, A. (2024a). Young farmers, small farms, and entrepreneurship under the new European Union Green Deal. *Annals of the University of Craiova*, XXVIX (LXX). <https://doi.org/10.52846/bihpt.v29i65.144>.
- Goulas, A., & Papachatzis, A. (2024b). Farm to Fork Strategy: A sustainable solution for rural communities. *Annals of the University of Craiova*, XXVIX (LXX). <https://doi.org/10.52846/bihpt.v29i65.143>.
- Guyomard, H., Soler, L.-G., Detang-Dessendre, C., & Requillart, V. (2023). The European Green Deal improves the sustainability of food systems but has uneven economic impacts on consumers and farmers. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-01019-6>.
- Kotyza, P. (2023). *European Green Deal and Farm-to-Fork strategy in the context of EU agricultural policy. In small farms managed by young farmers: Under new Farm-to-Fork strategy*. CeDeWu Sp. z. o. o.
- Pawlowski, K. P., & Soltysiak, G. (2024). The potential impact of the European Green Deal on farm production in Poland. *Sustainability*, 16(24). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su162411080>.